

MODELLING OF CRACK EVOLUTION UNDER CYCLIC THERMAL LOADING IN CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

C. HENAFF-GARDIN, M.C. LAFARIE-FRENOT, J.L. DESMEUZES
Laboratoire de Mécanique et de Physique des Matériaux, URA 863,
ENSMA, Site du Futuroscope, B.P. 109,
86960 FUTUROSCOPE CEDEX, FRANCE

ABSTRACT

An interlaminar shear stress analysis for progressive damage in composite laminates was developed. A general governing equation set was derived for $[0_m, 90_n]_s$ laminates that involves only in-plane displacements in both layers, based on equilibrium, continuity and boundary conditions. The case of cross-ply laminates with matrix cracks in both layers under biaxial tensile loading have been solved. Stress distributions, elastic constants and strain energy release rate have been obtained as functions of the crack densities in 0° and 90° layers of the laminate.

INTRODUCTION

In the space environment, advanced composite materials may experience important thermal cyclic loadings. Large thermal stresses may develop in composite structures due to the mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansions of adjacent plies at different orientations [1]. Thermal fatigue of long fibre composite laminates implies biaxial in-plane strains in each layer of the specimen (whatever its orientation is). So, thermal exposure is likely to enhance damages similar to those observed under mechanical loading [2]. In the case of cross-ply $[0_m, 90_n]_s$ stacking sequences, the thermal stresses inside the specimen lead to crack patterns which consist in matrix cracks along the fibers in both 0° and 90° plies [3].

Several analytical models have been developed in order to predict the damage evolution in cross-ply laminates submitted to uniaxial loading, the damage consisting in transverse cracks only. The most efficient analytical models, grouped under the "shear lag" designation, use different assumptions on the longitudinal displacement in the 90° ply [4-6]. Few authors have studied the case of cross-ply laminates submitted either to biaxial [7] or in-plane general loading [8], but with cracks only in 90° ply. Some analysis have also been carried out in $[\pm\theta/90^\circ]_s$ laminate with transverse cracks [9, 10].

The case of cross-ply composites with cracks in both layers has been studied under uniaxial tension [11] or under pure shear [12]. Tsai et al [13] have also proposed, under biaxial loading, an interlaminar-shear-lag analysis of a specimen with transverse and longitudinal cracks, the solution of this problem being the combination of the undisturbed solution with transverse cracks and that with longitudinal cracks.

The present study consists in a fracture mechanics analysis for the strain energy release rate associated with the 0° and 90° ply matrix crack formation under biaxial in-plane loading. In fact, we have chosen to extend an approach previously derived from a shear lag analysis proposed in [14]. An analogy is proposed between mechanical and thermal loading.

SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE CRACKED LAMINATES

In the present analysis, the studied cross-ply laminates are assumed to present a symmetric and periodic stacking sequence such as $[0_m, 90_n]_s$. The laminate is subjected to biaxial loading in both x and y directions. The z direction is that of the ply thickness (normal to the ply mean plane). The total 0° and 90° ply thicknesses are respectively noted $2t_0$ and $2t_{90}$.

Experimentally, the damage pattern observed under thermal cyclic loading [3] consists in a regular array of cracks along both 0° and 90° plies. In order to represent in a simple analytical way the crack distribution in the specimen, we have chosen two damage parameters : the crack density d_{90} in inner 90° layer, and d_0 in each outer 0° layer. The cell geometry used for modelling the specimen is given in Fig. 1. The cracks are assumed to be plane, normal to the x axis in the 90° layer (and to the y axis in the 0° plies). They are uniformly spaced along the traction directions x and y (the crack spacings $\frac{1}{d_0}$ and $\frac{1}{d_{90}}$ are independent one from the other). Then, we can consider that the laminate, which presents a double periodicity along both x and y axes, is constituted by a double stacking of "repeating unit cells" limited by two pairs of consecutive cracks in 0° and 90° plies (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 : Crack geometry used for modelling the thermal cracking in cross-ply laminates

Let us consider the displacements in the x and y directions in 90° layer (see Fig. 2). In the y direction (parallel to the 90° ply crack plane), we assume that the displacement is constant along z in the 90° layer thickness, and it is noted v^{90} . In the x direction (normal to the 90° ply crack plane), we suppose a parabolic evolution (Eqn. 1) of the displacement u with z (the minimum value of u being noted u^{90}).

The displacement expressions are analogous in the 0° plies (Eqn. 2). The out-of-plane displacements are neglected. The displacement fields are then given by the following expressions (where z is the laminate thickness direction co-ordinate) :

$$\text{in the } 90^\circ \text{ ply : } \begin{cases} u = u^{90} + \frac{z^2}{t_{90}^2} (u^0 - u^{90}) & \text{for } -t_{90} \leq z \leq +t_{90} \\ v = v^{90} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{in the } 0^\circ \text{ plies : } \begin{cases} u = u^0 \\ v = v^0 - \frac{(z - t_0 - t_{90})^2}{t_0^2} (v^0 - v^{90}) & \text{for } t_{90} \leq |z| \leq t_{90} + t_0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2 : Aspect of the displacement fields in the representative unit cell

The average (through the thickness) in-plane displacements in the two layers are obtained by integration of Eqns (1) and (2) :

$$\overline{u^{90}} = \frac{u^0 + 2u^{90}}{3} \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{v^0} = \frac{2v^0 + v^{90}}{3} \quad (3)$$

The distortions at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface are then given by :

$$\gamma_{xz}^i = \left. \frac{du}{dz} \right|_{z=t_{90}} = \frac{3}{t_{90}} (u^0 - \overline{u^{90}}) \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{yz}^i = \left. \frac{dv}{dz} \right|_{z=t_{90}} = \frac{3}{t_0} (\overline{v^0} - v^{90}) \quad (4)$$

EQUILIBRIUM CONDITIONS IN THE CRACKED LAYERS

In the case of biaxial tensile loading (σ_x and σ_y are the stresses applied to the laminate, respectively along the x and y direction), equilibrium conditions on the free body layer element allow to obtain the following out-of-plane shear interface stresses τ_{xz}^i and τ_{yz}^i expressions :

$$\tau_{xz}^i = G_{23} \gamma_{xz}^i = t_0 \frac{\partial \sigma_x^0}{\partial x} = -t_{90} \frac{\partial \sigma_x^{90}}{\partial x} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_{yz}^i = G_{23} \gamma_{yz}^i = t_0 \frac{\partial \sigma_y^0}{\partial y} = -t_{90} \frac{\partial \sigma_y^{90}}{\partial y} \quad (5)$$

where G_{23} is the out of plane shear modulus of a ply, and σ_j^{θ} are the ply stresses along the j direction, in the θ° plies.

After deriving the preceding Eqns (5), and when applying constitutive equations (6) in 0° and 90° plies :

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} = \frac{\sigma_x^0}{E_1} - \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_y^0, & \epsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_x^0 + \frac{\sigma_y^0}{E_2}, \\ \epsilon_x^{90} &= \frac{\partial u^{90}}{\partial x} = -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_y^{90} + \frac{\sigma_x^{90}}{E_2}, & \epsilon_y^{90} &= \frac{\partial v^{90}}{\partial y} = \frac{\sigma_y^{90}}{E_1} - \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_x^{90} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

we obtain the following system of governing equations in which the σ_x^0 and σ_y^0 stresses appear to depend on both variables x and y :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_x^0}{\partial x^2} - \lambda_x^2 \sigma_x^0 = -\mu_x^2 \sigma_y^0 - \mu_x^2 \left(\frac{E_1}{\nu_{12} E_2} \sigma_x - \sigma_y \right) \\ \frac{\partial^2 \sigma_y^0}{\partial y^2} - \lambda_y^2 \sigma_y^0 = -\mu_y^2 \sigma_x^0 - \mu_y^2 \left(-\sigma_x + \frac{1}{\nu_{12}} \sigma_y \right) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \begin{cases} \lambda_x^2 = \frac{3G_{23}}{t_0 t_{90}^2} \frac{(t_0 E_1 + t_{90} E_2)}{E_1 E_2} \\ \lambda_y^2 = \frac{3G_{23}}{t_0^2 t_{90}} \frac{(t_{90} E_1 + t_0 E_2)}{E_1 E_2} \end{cases} \text{ and } \begin{cases} \mu_x^2 = \frac{3G_{23}}{t_0 t_{90}^2} (t_0 + t_{90}) \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \\ \mu_y^2 = \frac{3G_{23}}{t_0^2 t_{90}} (t_0 + t_{90}) \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \end{cases}$$

E_1, E_2, ν_{12} are respectively the longitudinal modulus, transverse modulus and Poisson's ratio of an uncracked ply. $\lambda_x, \lambda_y, \mu_x, \mu_y$, are parameters representative of material and of the laminate geometry.

STRESSES IN THE CRACKED LAYERS

The resolution of the above system of differential equations (15) will allow us to obtain the ply stress values everywhere in the laminate. The boundary conditions can be written as follows :

In the 0° layer, the average normal stress is equal to zero at the 0° ply crack edges, so we have :

$$d_{90} \int_{x=-\frac{1}{2d_{90}}}^{x=+\frac{1}{2d_{90}}} \sigma_y^0 \left(x, y = \pm \frac{1}{2d_0} \right) dx = 0 \quad (8)$$

Moreover, in the 0° layer, near a 90° ply crack $\left(x = \pm \frac{1}{2d_{90}} \right)$, the stress transfer implies :

$$d_0 \int_{y=-\frac{1}{2d_0}}^{y=+\frac{1}{2d_0}} \sigma_x^0 \left(x = \pm \frac{1}{2d_0}, y \right) dy = \frac{t_0 + t_{90}}{t_0} \sigma_x. \quad (9)$$

The preceding differential equations (7) can then be completely solved :

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_x^0 = A \cosh(R\lambda_x x) + B \cosh(R\lambda_y y) + K_x \\ \sigma_y^0 = A \frac{\nu_{12} E_2 (t_0 + t_{90})}{t_0 E_1 + t_{90} E_2} \cosh(R\lambda_x x) + B \frac{t_{90} E_1 + t_0 E_2}{\nu_{12} E_2 (t_0 + t_{90})} \cosh(R\lambda_y y) + K_y \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where R, A, B, K_x, K_y are functions of geometric (t₀, t₉₀) and damage (d₀, d₉₀) parameters, of ply elastic constant initial values (E₁, E₂, ν₁₂) and of the applied stresses (σ_x, σ_y).

ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF THE CRACKED LAMINATE

The condition of displacement $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_y$ continuity in the cracked laminate allows us to obtain the expressions of the damaged longitudinal E₁^{θc}, transverse E₂^{θc} moduli values and ν₁₂^{θc} and ν₂₁^{θc}

Poisson's ratio values of the cracked θ° (θ = 0°, 90°) plies. We assume that,

in the 0° ply, E₁^{0c}, E₂^{0c}, ν₁₂^{0c} only depend on d₀ spacing,
and in the 90° ply, E₁^{90c}, E₂^{90c}, ν₁₂^{90c} only depend on d₉₀ spacing.

It appears that, in both 0° and 90° plies, the longitudinal modulus E₁^{θc} remains constant (equal to the initial value E₁), whereas transverse modulus E₂^{θc} decreases with increasing dθ. Moreover, ν₁₂^{θc} remains also constant and ν₂₁^{θc} decreases.

In these conditions, the cracked laminate characteristics E_x^c, E_y^c, ν_{xy}^c, ν_{yx}^c are all decreasing when cracks develop. Note that E_y^c, ν_{yx}^c only depend on d₀, whereas E_x^c, ν_{xy}^c are functions of the only

damage parameter d₉₀ (see examples on Fig. 3). Moreover, it appears that the ratios $\frac{\nu_{xy}^c}{E_x^c}$ and

$\frac{\nu_{yx}^c}{E_y^c}$ remain constants whatever the damage state is.

Figure 3 : Evolutions of longitudinal stiffness and major Poisson's ratio of a cracked [04/904]_S T300/914 carbon/epoxy laminate.

STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE

A fracture mechanics analysis is then applied to develop a tool capable of predictions onset of matrix cracking . The cracked surface variation is related to the strain energy release rate under mode I opening, G_I , which is defined as

$$G_I = \left(\frac{\partial U_{el}}{\partial S_c} \right)_{\sigma} \tag{11}$$

where U_{el} and S_c are respectively the stored elastic energy and the cracked surface area in an elementary volume of the specimen. We have :

$$S_c = \frac{t_0 d_0 + t_{90} d_{90}}{t_0 + t_{90}} \quad \text{and} \quad U_{el} = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_x \bar{\epsilon}_x + \sigma_y \bar{\epsilon}_y) \tag{12}$$

$$\text{so} \quad G_I = \frac{t_0 + t_{90}}{2} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\sigma_x^2}{E_x^c} + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{E_y^c} - 2 \frac{v_{xy}^c}{E_x^c} \sigma_x \sigma_y \right)}{\partial (t_0 d_0 + t_{90} d_{90})} = \frac{t_0 + t_{90}}{2} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{\sigma_x^2}{E_x^c} + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{E_y^c} \right)}{\partial (t_0 d_0 + t_{90} d_{90})} \tag{13}$$

because $\frac{v_{xy}^c}{E_x^c}$ remains constant.

In order to study damage evolution, we consider the initiation of a new crack, either in 0° or 90° plies, while the number of cracks remains constant in the other ply. In these conditions, the above expression of the strain energy release rate may be simplified as follows :
 in the case of a crack initiation in the 90° plies (d_0 remains constant, d_{90} is varying):

$$G_I = \frac{t_0 + t_{90}}{2 t_{90}} \sigma_x^2 \frac{\partial \left(\frac{1}{E_x^c} \right)}{\partial d_{90}} = - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_x^2}{(E_x^c)^2} \frac{dE_2^{90c}}{dd_{90}} \tag{14}$$

The expression is strictly analogous when considering 0° ply crack formation :

$$G_I = \frac{t_0 + t_{90}}{2 t_0} \sigma_y^2 \frac{\partial \left(\frac{1}{E_y^c} \right)}{\partial d_0} = - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_y^2}{(E_y^c)^2} \frac{dE_2^{0c}}{dd_0} \tag{15}$$

The Eqns (14) and (15) can be applied to a laminate submitted to biaxial strain loading ($\overline{\epsilon_x}$, $\overline{\epsilon_y}$) by using the constitutive equations (16) in the laminate :

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_x = \frac{E_x^c \overline{\epsilon_x} + \nu_{xy}^c E_y^c \overline{\epsilon_y}}{1 - (\nu_{xy}^c)^2} \\ \sigma_y = \frac{\nu_{yx}^c E_x^c \overline{\epsilon_x} + E_y^c \overline{\epsilon_y}}{1 - (\nu_{yx}^c)^2} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

APPLICATION TO THERMAL FATIGUE

Let's consider now the experimental tests conducted on a cross-ply laminate submitted to cyclic temperature variations. In order to apply the preceding analysis, it is necessary to make an analogy between thermal and biaxial mechanical loading. The theory proposed by Datoo [15] allows to calculate the strains in each ply of an uncracked laminate submitted to temperature variations ΔT (with taking into account the thermal residual stresses). For example, in the case of a $[0_4/90_4]_S$ T300/914 laminate, thermal strains are equal to $-1.89 \cdot 10^{-5} \Delta T$ along the fibres, and $2.06 \cdot 10^{-5} \Delta T$ perpendicular to the fibres. In these conditions, we choose an equivalent mechanical loading $\overline{\epsilon_x} = \overline{\epsilon_y} = 2.06 \cdot 10^{-5} \Delta T$ along both 0° and 90° directions.

Figure 4 : Mode I strain energy release rate evolutions versus crack density in $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminates submitted to thermal cycling at different temperature amplitudes ΔT .

It appears that for every temperature amplitude, the strain energy release rate decreases with increasing crack density. The initiation of new cracks becomes more and more difficult with the increase of damage. Moreover, for a given crack density, G increases with ΔT : the generation of new cracks is easier and faster under thermal cycling at high amplitudes. These results are analogous to those obtained under fatigue mechanical loading [14].

On Fig. 4, the critical value of the strain energy release rate G_{Ic} determined by quasi-static loading experiments has also been reported. Above this value, cracks can initiate from the first thermal cycle. Below this value, a few thermal cycles are necessary to initiate cracks in the specimen. When G_I is far below G_{Ic} , no damage evolution is observed, even after many cycles. This modelling has been compared with experimental results presented elsewhere [3], and a very good agreement has been observed.

CONCLUSIONS

An analysis for progressive damage evolution in cross-ply composite laminates is developed. The specimen is submitted to biaxial tensile in-plane loading, and the resulting damage consists in matrix cracks along the fibres in both 0° and 90° directions. The modelling is based on a shear lag analysis, with parabolic displacements in the cracked layers. Equilibrium, continuity and boundary conditions then allow to obtain the expressions of the stress distributions, of the elastic constants of the damaged specimen, and of the strain energy release rate under mode I opening. All these expressions are functions of the material properties, of the laminate geometry and of the crack density values.

The results concerning strain energy release rate show a very good agreement with experimental results under thermal fatigue [3].

REFERENCES

1. P. Aswendt and R. Hofling, Speckle interferometry for analysing anisotropic thermal expansion - application to specimens and components. *Composites* **24** (8), 611-617 (1993).
2. D.S. Forsyth, S.O. Kasap, I. Wacker, and S. Yannacopoulos, Thermal fatigue of composites - ultrasonic and SEM evaluations. *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology - Transactions of the ASME* **116** (1), 113-120 (1994).
3. M.C. Lafarie-Frenot, C. Henaff-Gardin, and V.L. Tahiri. Evolution of fatigue damage in various carbon/epoxy laminates. in *7th Int. Conf. on mechanical behaviour of materials*, May 28 - June 2 1995, The Hague, The Netherlands, (1995).
4. L. Boniface, S.L. Ogin, and P.A. Smith, The change in thermal expansion coefficient as a damage parameter during thermal cycling of crossply laminates, in *Composite materials : fatigue and fracture. Fourth volume*, W.W. Stinchomb and N.E. Ashbaugh, Editors, American Society for Testing of Materials, ASTM STP 1156, 139-160. (1993).
5. S.G. Lim and C.S. Hong, Effect of transverse cracks on the thermomechanical properties of cross-ply laminated composites. *Composite Sciences and Technology* **34**, 145-162 (1989).
6. F.J. Guild, S.L. Ogin, and P.A. Smith, Modelling of 90° ply cracking in crossply laminates, including three-dimensional effects. *J. of Composite Materials* **27** (7), 646-667 (1993).
7. L.N. McCartney, The prediction of cracking in biaxially loaded cross-ply laminates having brittle matrices. *Composites* **24** (2), 84-92 (1993).
8. J. Renard, J.P. Favre, and T. Jeggy, Influence of transverse cracking on ply behavior : introduction of a characteristic damage variable. *Composites Science and Technology* **46**, 39-37 (1993).
9. R.J. Nuismer and S.C. Tan, Constitutive relations of a cracked composite lamina. *Journal of Composite Materials* **22**, 306-321 (1988).
10. J. Zhang, J. Fan, and C. Soutis, Analysis of multiple matrix cracking in $(\pm\theta_m/90_n)_s$ composite laminates .1. In-Plane stiffness properties. *Composites* **23** (5), 291-298 (1992).
11. Z. Hashin, Analysis of orthogonally cracked laminates under tension. *Journal of Applied Mechanics* **54**, 872-879 (1987).
12. C.L. Tsai and I.M. Daniel, The behavior of cracked cross-ply composite laminates under shear loading. *International Journal of Solids and structures* **29** (24), 3251-3267 (1992).
13. C.L. Tsai, I.M. Daniel, and J.W. Lee. Progressive matrix cracking of crossply composite laminates under biaxial loading. in *Winter annual meeting of the ASME*, Dallas, Texas: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, AMD vol 111 MD vol 22, 9-18, (1990).
14. C. Henaff-Gardin, M.C. Lafarie-Frenot, J. Brillaud, and A. El Mahi, Influence of the stacking sequence on fatigue transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates, in *Damage detection in composite materials*, J.E. Masters, Editor, American Society for Testing and Materials: Philadelphia, ASTM STP 1128, 26-255. (1992).
15. M.H. Dato, Residual stresses, in *Mechanics of fibrous composites*, Elsevier Applied Science, 367-. (1991).